

A COMMON, OPEN SOURCE INTERFACE
BETWEEN EARTH OBSERVATION DATA
INFRASTRUCTURES AND FRONT-END
APPLICATIONS

Deliverable 03

OPERATIVE ONLINE
DISSEMINATION PORTALS

TECHNISCHE
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1 INTRODUCTION

The openEO project has made firm promises about opening its communications in order to become visible in a very early stage, and be inviting for others to get involved in the development of the openEO API. This deliverable, D2.1 “Operative online dissemination portals” which is delivered in the third month of the project shows which measures have been taken during the first three months of the project to realise this goal. The dissemination measures we describe here include (i) website and blog, (ii) social networks, and (iii) source code sharing platform.

2 WEBSITE AND BLOG

2.1 Motivating blog and initial website

The blog “OpenEO: a GDAL for Earth Observation Analytics”, authored by main openEO proposal writers (Edzer Pebesma, Wolfgang Wagner, Jan Verbesselt, Erwin Goor, Christian Briese, Markus Neteler) and found at <http://r-spatial.org/2016/11/29/openeo.html> was written as a blueprint for the openEO project proposal, days after this group met in Vienna and decided to prepare this proposal. The blog post was shared over twitter, using the hashtag #openEO, and widely read. It received 2,377 page views by Dec 15, 2017 (google analytics). At the same time, the domain openeo.org was registered and the GitHub organisation github.com/Open-EO was claimed (github.com/openEO not being available). The openeo.org website only contained the project logo, and redirected to the GitHub organisation. openEO-related activities, such as the first openEO hackathon in Muenster, held Mar 23-24, 2017, received also an entry¹ on the popular <http://r-spatial.org/> blog. Results of this hackathon were added to the github.com/Open-EO organisation.

Directly after the news that the openEO project was funded, the <http://openeo.org/> website was filled with initial content (see <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo.org>), including:

- Project title
- Project number
- Funding scheme and call

Figure 1: openeo.org website traffic over time

¹ <http://r-spatial.org/r/2017/04/19/first-openeo-hackaton.html>

- Proposal abstract
- List of partners and consortium members

After the kick-off meeting, a tweet with a picture of the people present at the kickoff meeting was added.

By Dec 15, 2017 the openEO project website, <http://openeo.org/> has received 704 page views in total (google analytics). Figure 1 shows the website traffic over time.

The domain <http://openeo.org> was chosen to stress that the project aims at an open development process, and will create open source software: .org websites have this association, .eu websites do not. In addition, the scope of the project is not limited to the EU. The domain <http://openeo.eu> has also been registered and currently redirects to <http://openeo.org/>.

2.2 Sharing of project proposal

During the kick-off meeting of openEO Oct 12-13, 2017 in Vienna, it was decided that the project proposal (or the “description of actions” document) was going to be published, after removing the effort tables and financial information. A version ready for publication was circulated before publication, and all partners were requested to add the names of those who contributed to the author list. On Nov 23, 2017 the document has been published on Zenodo² and now has a DOI³ as well as is linked to and from OpenAIRE. The publication has been added to the initial website, and has been tweeted. Zenodo does not provide download or access statistics.

2.3 „Second phase“ web site

The initial website consisted of a single html page. Early December 2017 this has been replaced by a static website with different tabs. The opening page reveals the logo, the tabs, and links to a RSS feed, the EU logo and grant number, a link to a twitter handle and to the GitHub organisation, and a project one-liner (“openEO develops an open API to connect R, python and JavaScript clients to big Earth observation cloud back-ends in a simple and unified way.”)

The project tabs can be trivially altered or extended, and currently include:

- About (project title, number, call, duration, proposal summary, some tweets with pictures of members)
- Partners (including pointing out the consortium members receiving H2020 funding)
- Info (links to the proposal, to the initiating blog, OpenAIRE and ResearchGate openEO links, the Open-EO GitHub organisation and a pointer to a discussion forum on the GitHub organisation)
- Glossary (work in progress: a list of words and their definitions as well as links to synonyms; meant as an agreement to choose a set of terms to be used in the rest of the project).

The setup of the website is that of a blog, and we plan to regularly post updates on recent activities, discussions, additions and other news as short blog posts. I first blog post reporting on the “first week of intense collaboration”, held at VITO, Dec 4-6, has been posted as of Dec, 2017.

² <https://zenodo.org/record/1065474>

³ 10.5281/zenodo.1065474

3 SOCIAL NETWORKS

Although the project proposal mentions Facebook and Google+ as potential networks, so far activities have been limited to:

- Twitter
- Github
- Website

The reasons to not go for Facebook or Google+ are that these platforms are less used for professional purposes, are less used by (and tailored to) software developers, and are by no means associated with data science or open source software development.

Twitter activities include:

- Using the #openEO hashtag before we had our own handle
- Tweeting from @Open_EO in the name of the project
- Retweeting using personal and institutional accounts

Twitter activities using the hashtag and the handle are listed in two appendices.

The GitHub social network platform include:

- Everyone can get an account on GitHub, either anonymous or named
- Everyone with an account can create or react to issues
- Issues can be short reports of something that doesn't work or seems to be missing, or be simple questions, or can be discussions about a large topic.
- Issues can very easily refer (link) to other issues, and code fragments and pictures can very easily be included.

Although there is some criticism about the flexibility of GitHub to hold discussions (in particular: the inability to branch discussions, and react to particular issue responses), in openEO we have not run into its limitation. If this limitation may become visible, we may decide to open a Gitter⁴ community, which is also free and open. Issues in twitter can easily be integrated with a kanban-board style project management tool, "GitHub projects", and the openEO group has committed to start using that when interactions become more intensive.

An initial discussion forum was started as a GitHub repository⁵. It is meant as a point to raise generic openEO issues, not specific to a particular software component, but to the project as a whole. The GitHub repository was chosen for this to make it easier for developers, since most developers are familiar with discussion through raising issues at GitHub.

4 SOURCE CODE SHARING PLATFORM

All the code developed within openEO that is worth sharing with the community at large (including web site, general discussions repository and glossary) is available at the <https://github.com/Open-EO/> organisation. As of Dec 15, 2017, the organisations contains 15 repositories (see appendix for a listing); this is not to be seen as a sign of quality, but in any case as a sign that the consortium members feel comfortable with sharing developed code instantly with a global readership.

⁴ <https://gitter.im/>

⁵ <https://github.com/Open-EO/discuss>

The organisation has currently 16 members; it should be noted that not all members are paid by project funding, which indicates that others are already involved, and that there is already a trust between consortium members and external contributors. Not all organisation members are visible on the GitHub page: visibility is by default off, and members have to actively switch on that they are visible as a member. Appendix 3 lists all organisation members.

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1. Tweets from @Open_EO
2. Tweets with hashtag #openEO
3. GitHub Open-EO organisation: list of members (December 2017)
4. GitHub Open-EO organisation: list of repositories (December 2017)

Tweets 4 Following 17 Followers 51 Likes 1

Following

openEO

@open_EO Follows you

openEO - A Common, Open Source Interface between Earth Observation Data Infrastructures and Front-End Applications

openeo.org

Joined November 2017

Tweet to

Message

13 Followers you know

Photos and videos

Tweets Tweets & replies Media

openEO @open_EO · Dec 5

First week of intense collaboration for #openEO @VITO_RS_, drafting a first API and doing use cases. @MundialisInfo @EODC_GmbH #ifgi @CopernicusEU @sinergise @EURAC #JRC

13

23

Retweeted

Chris Holmes @opencholmes · Nov 29

Excited to welcome wider collaboration on the SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog specification a group of us have been working on - medium.com/@cholmes/annou... The Cloud Native Geospatial future will be interoperable. 🌍📡🚀 Thanks to @OurRadiantEarth and @planetlabs for the support!

Announcing the SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) specification

The STAC GitHub repository is 'open for business', to collaboratively build interoperability among imagery and other geo data providers.

medium.com

🗨️ ↻️ 23 35 📧

openEO @open_EO · Nov 23

We published our @open_EO project proposal at zenodo.org/record/1065474 @EUJH2020 @EU_H2020 @CopernicusData @EO_OPEN_SCIENCE #openEO

OpenEO - a Common, Open Source Interface Betwe...

Project proposal (without effort tables) of the openEO project, see <http://openeo.org/> . openEO - A Common, Open Source Interface between Earth Observation Data zenodo.org

🗨️ ↻️ 1 3 📧

Promoted Tweet

Sanofi @sanofi · Dec 13

Sanofi ist ein lebenslanger Begleiter in Gesundheitsfragen. #EmpoweringLife

🌐 Translate from German

Sanofi Empowering Life
www.sanofi-empowering-life.com

🚩 Promoted

🗨️ ↻️ 1 22 📧

↻️ openEO Retweeted

Edzer Pebesma @edzerpebesma · Oct 13

openEO is kicking off in Vienna! #openeo @EU_H2020 @CopernicusEU @MarkusNeteler @appelmar @janverbesselt @EODC_GmbH openeo.org

1 17 27

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Martin Su... ×

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1,614 Tweets

[#InnoDay](#)
2,213 Tweets

[#Israel](#)
13.8K Tweets

[#Berlinale](#)

[Martin Schulz](#)
1,097 Tweets

[Sondierungen](#)

[#Steinmeier](#)

[#Messe](#)

[#ArtGold](#)
1,091 Tweets

#openeo

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Martin Maechler @MMae... ×

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Arun Srinivasan @arun_... ×

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S Milton Bache @ste... ×

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Trends for you · Change

#MagentaMusik360

Westernhagen im kostenlosen Livestream - heute ab 20:15 Uhr!

Promoted by MagentaMusik 360

#CSUPT17

Insolvenz
1,621 Tweets

#InnoDay
2,154 Tweets

#UdLDigital

#Berlinale

Martin Schulz
1,155 Tweets

Herbst 2020

#Steinmeier

#Sondierungen

CEOS @CEOSdotORG · Sep 13

Day 1 under way! #openEO #EarthObservation

ESA EarthObservation @ESA_EO

Group picture of @CEOSdotORG 2017 SIT Technical Workshop (13-14 September) at #ESRIN in #Frascati, #Italy.

ceos.org/meetings/2017-...

1 retweet 5 replies

Tyler Erickson follows

Panagiotis Tziachris @PanagiotisTzia · Oct 13

Interesting: #openeo.

However, are "cloud environments" ready to shift from integration to modularity? (good enough?)

r-spatial.org/2016/11/29/ope...

1 retweet 0 replies

CEOS @CEOSdotORG · Sep 12

Adam Lewis (@GeoscienceAus) on using #AnalysisReadyData for #atmosphere & #ocean applications. #OpenEO #EarthObservation #VCWGDAY @ESA_EO

#openeo

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2 5 8

TimSalabim and 3 others follow

Chris Reudenbach @creuden · 30 Nov 2016

Replying to @edzerpebesma

#OpenEO perfect thanks. Up to now no Idea but I did not screen the calls. usually the BMBF is easier

1

timelyportfolio follows

Garry Jenkin @grjenkin · Oct 1

Read SPATIAL ANALYTICS TODAY ▶ #futureeo #openeo
paper.li/merapps/136239...

Ben Marwick and 1 other liked

Daniel Nüst @nordholmen · Apr 28

Replying to @nordholmen @niallhrobinson and 2 others

@niallhrobinson Final question on competing systems for #Earth #bigdata reminded me of #OpenEO r-spatial.org/2016/11/29/ope... by @edzerpebesma

Open EO Interface: the 20's

The following figure shows schematically how this could look like: Users write scripts in a neutral language that addresses the data and operations, but ignores the computer architecture of the back-end. The back-end carries out the computations and returns results. It needs to be able to identify users (e.g. verify its permission to use it), but also to tell which data they provide and which computational operations they afford.

1 3

Edzer Pebesma @edzerpebesma · Jul 4

#openeo

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OpenEO is kicking off in Vienna: #OpenEO @EO_H2020 @CopernicusEO @MarkusNeteler @appelmar @janverbesselt @EODC_GmbH openeo.org

1 17 27

CEOS @CEOSdotORG · Sep 12

It's CEOS Virtual Constellation / Working Group Day! #EarthObservations #OpenEO ceos.org/ourwork/

4

Edzer Pebesma @edzerpebesma · Jan 20

First #OpenEO hackaton will be held @ ifgi on Mar 23-24. Let me know if you're interested to participate! r-spatial.org/2016/11/29/ope...

1 4 4

Majin Lamp @MajinLamp76 · 2 Jan 2016

Replying to @MajinLamp76

Running she started screaming "Fueling WFE ABC" As she screamed it she

Running she started screaming, "Fucking WEEABOO!" AS she screamed it she ate a piece of candy everytime she said it. #OpenEo

#openeo

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1 29 48 |||

Edzer Pebesma @edzerpebesma · Nov 14

openEO now has its own twitter handle! @openEO #openEO

1 1 |||

[Show this thread](#)

Edzer Pebesma @edzerpebesma · Oct 15

Three year research associate position available in my lab for the #openEO project; react fast: uni-muenster.de/Rektorat/Stell...

33 19 |||

Edzer Pebesma @edzerpebesma · 30 Nov 2016

Replying to @mouthofmorrison @azavea @geotrellis

Cool! So together with GeoTrellis back-end you form one of the columns of the fourth figure? #OpenEO

1 1 |||

HUB Remote Sensing follows

Hadi @HadiEOind · Oct 1

Exciting, and necessary, #FutureEO development to watch for: #openEO - a GDAL for EO analytics

r-spatial.org/2016/11/29/ope...

1 1 |||

Edzer Pebesma @edzerpebesma · Nov 14

You just need to know how to find it: @open_EO #openeo

1 1 |||

[Show this thread](#)

Jeroen Dries @jeroen_dries · Dec 6

Just wrapped up first #H2020 #openeo code Sprint @VITObelgium great team!

Looking forward to bringing this to @PROBAVegetation #MEP!

2 2 |||

Edzer Pebesma @edzerpebesma · 30 Nov 2016

Replying to @creuden

Maybe start here, and keep the #OpenEO tag?

2 1 |||

Edzer Pebesma @edzerpebesma · Sep 21

Replying to @FiveTwoN

to be found under #openEO , project summary right now at openeo.org

1 1 |||

Jan Verbesselt @ianverbesselt · 30 Nov 2016

Making easy analysis of large amounts of satellite data possible with #OpenEO by a #GDAL + #computing = GDAL on steroids

#openeo

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5 11

Markus Neteler Retweeted

Mundialis GmbH & Co. @MundialisInfo · Jul 4

Glad to be part of the #openeo team! #EU_H2020 #CopernicusEU #grassgis #rsatial

Edzer Pebesma @edzerpebesma

Our @EU_H2020 #openeo proposal got 2M funding: great endorsement, and a big responsibility. r-spatial.org/2016/11/29/ope... @CopernicusEU #rsatial

1 2

The Yob @TheYob1 · Aug 7

#openeo #customerservice #tyres what a joke this company, do not buy from them!

1

Michael Sumner Retweeted

giovanni allegri @_giohappy_ · Jul 5

2M fundings to #openeo. Congrats, great job! r-spatial.org/2016/11/29/ope... #EU_H2020 @CopernicusEU

2 2

Edzer Pebesma @edzerpebesma · Nov 23

Spatiotemporal arrays for R - first stars blog: r-spatial.org/r/2017/11/23/s... #rstats #rsatial #openEO @open EO @mdsummer @tiennebr @RConsortium

28 74

Jeroen Dries and 6 others Retweeted

openEO @open_EO · Dec 5

First week of intense collaboration for #openEO @VITO_RS_, drafting a first API and doing use cases. @MundialisInfo @EODC_GmbH #ifgi @CopernicusEU @sinergise @EURAC #JRC

13 23

Edzer Pebesma @edzerpebesma · Nov 23

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Project proposal (without short abstract) of the openEO project, see <http://openeo.org/> . openEO - A Common, Open Source Interface between Earth Observation Data zenodo.org

6
 10

TopCode.io @TopCodensation · Mar 29

#TopCode on démarre zen #yoga #bootcamp #openeo

<https://www.pscp.tv/TopCodensation/1ynJOWwOyQkJR>

ENDED 105 Viewers

TopCode.io @TopCodensation

#TopCode on démarre zen #yoga #bootcamp #openeo
pscp.tv

2

TopCode.io @TopCodensation · Mar 27

#TopCode #bootcamp #OpeNeo phase3 la nuit commence !! Problème a résoudre pour demain matin 8 heures.... :D

Translate from French

#openeo

- Top
- Latest
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1 3

Nicolas Cailleaud @nicokayo · Jan 12

A tous ceux qui veulent devenir les "Maverick" du #Code un petit tour chez @TopCodensation s'impose ! #OpéNeo

Translate from French

TopCode, une formation pour devenir développeur de l'extrême

Avec ses méthodes inspirées des escape games et des sports extrêmes, TopCode entend former la crème des développeurs en France. Celle-ci lan...
cnewsmatin.fr

3 3

TopCode.io @TopCodensation · Jan 11

#Follow @TopCodeNation+#RT pr participer au #concours #OpéNeo
gagnez 10 places au bootcamp pr devenir développeur
topcode.io

Translate from French

Follow @TopCodeNation et #RT ce message
pour tenter de gagner l'une des 10 places pour

OPÉRATION NÉO

Bootcamp de 5 jours pour vous initier
aux joies du développement

Postulez sur www.topcode.in

#openeo

- Top**
- Latest
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Patricia Salvador @PatriciaSalGar · 13 Mar 2012

Replying to @MeliisaLoVa
@melisa_love14 te #openeo por #whatsapp jijji *_*

Translate from Spanish

Jan Verbesselt liked

openEO @open_EO · Nov 23

We published our @open_EO project proposal at zenodo.org/record/1065474 @EUJH2020 @EU_H2020 @CopernicusData @EO_OPEN_SCIENCE #openEO

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Open-EO

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Settings

Find a member...

Members

Outside collaborators

Invite member

<input type="checkbox"/> Select all		2FA	Role				
<input type="checkbox"/>							
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<http://openeo.org/>

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👤 People 18
👥 Teams 0
📁 Projects 1
⚙️ Settings

Type: All ▾
Language: All ▾
Customize pinned repositories
New

openeo-wcps-driver

Java Apache-2.0 Updated a day ago

openeo-grassgis-driver

OpenEO driver for GRASS GIS
 Apache-2.0 Updated a day ago

openeo.org

openeo.org landing page
 CSS Updated 4 days ago

glossary

glossary for openEO: <http://openeo.org/glossary/>
 CSS ★ 2 Updated 7 days ago

openeo-sentinelhub-driver

JavaScript 1 Updated 9 days ago

back_offices_overview

Overview document about back offices metadata standards and interfaces
 Apache-2.0 Updated 9 days ago

openeo-api-poc

Prototypical core API for OpenEO proof of concept
 ★ 2 2 Apache-2.0 Updated 9 days ago

openeo-python-client

Python client API for OpenEO
 Python ★ 4 Updated 10 days ago

Top languages

Python Java CSS
 JavaScript HTML

People

18 >

Invite someone

[openeo-jeodpp-driver](#)

OpenEO driver for JEODPP

🔗 Apache-2.0 Updated 10 days ago

[openeo-geopyspark-driver](#)

OpenEO driver for GeoPySpark (Geotrellis)

Python 🔗 Apache-2.0 Updated 10 days ago

[openeo-python-driver](#)

Common parts of a Python driver implementation for OpenEO

Python 🔗 Apache-2.0 Updated 10 days ago

[openeo-geotrellis-driver](#)

Geotrellis driver implementation for OpenEO

Java 🔗 Apache-2.0 Updated 16 days ago

[software_guidelines](#)

openeo software guidelines

🔗 2 🔗 Apache-2.0 Updated 29 days ago

[open-eo.github.io](#)

landing page

HTML Updated on Mar 21

[discuss](#)

use issues to bring up discussion items related to the Open-EO Initiative

★ 7 Updated on Nov 30, 2016

